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IMPACT OF BOSS PHUBBING ON SUBORDINATE PERCEIVED WORK ALIENATION THROUGH EMPLOYEES' SELF-EFFICACY

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between boss phubbing (snubbing subordinates through mobile phone use in their presence) and subordinates' perceived work alienation, with self-efficacy as a mediating factor. The research model of this study is based on Affective Events Theory (AET), which explains the dynamics of boss phubbing, employee self-efficacy, and employees' perceived work alienation. An adopted questionnaire was used to collect data from 486 banking employees. Hypotheses were developed based on the existing literature, duly supported by theory. The SMART-PLS 4.0 was used for data analysis employing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). This study can help identify the critical factors related to the practice of phubbing. Policymakers can formulate policies to minimize the adverse impact of phubbing on financial institutions and eliminate its influence in the public sector.

Keywords: Boss Phubbing, Employee Self Efficacy, Employees' Perceived Work Alienation

1. Introduction

In recent years, the workplace of the future has undergone significant changes. This change may be linked to the rapid growth of technology and the increasing use of smartphones. Originally intended to simplify communication, organization, and productivity, this technology is widely accepted; nevertheless, its prevalence has blurred the line between our personal and professional lives (Elsa et al., 2025). In companies, particularly in highly regulated industries such as banking, the use of smartphones has affected the quality of communication between leaders and employees (Campanella et al., 2015). Because they mediate the psychological experiences workers have on the job, these variances, which are, in many cases, relatively slight, are increasingly being viewed as a serious concern in organizational behavior research (Jahangir et al., 2025; Peng & Chan, 2019; Youssef & Luthans, 2007). In the office environment, the act of phubbing, which involves ignoring someone while being engrossed in one's phone, has infiltrated workplaces and evolved into a specific form called boss phubbing. This occurs when managers disregard their employees while simultaneously engaging in conversation with them at the same time (Aman-Ullah et al., 2025; Khan et al., 2021; Yousaf et al., 2022). Current behavioral trends require academic attention, as supervisory communication is the spine of employee motivation, performance, and commitment to the organization.

With greater global commercial competition and an increased demand for the 'workforce' to deliver more productivity than in previous decades, employee engagement is now becoming the existential priority that senior leaders must be almost quixotically obsessed with (Bashir et al., 2010; Yavaş, 2024). Studies consistently demonstrate that employees' sense of justice, acknowledgment, and respect for one another are powerful drivers of their motivation and engagement.

Conversely, the value of employee-oriented management techniques is growing, even as behaviors that compromise relationship quality in more subtle ways, such as technological distraction, become more challenging to identify (Bilderback, 2024). Gallup's findings on workplace employee engagement in Pakistan are similarly gloomy. These surveys consistently show that only a minuscule fraction of the workforce in Pakistan has a significant connection to their places of employment (Saleem et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022). This kind of disengagement is suggestive of more fundamental psychological processes that hinder workers' emotional functioning. These processes

create obstacles to workers' emotional operations. Understanding the reasons behind the negative psychological states caused by new communication diversions, such as phubbing, is essential for preserving workplace morale and productivity. This knowledge is essential for sustaining morale and productivity in the workplace.

(Khattak et al., 2022) found that the superior-subordinate relationship is crucial to the fulfilment of tasks in an organization, so we need to explore the factors that really affect the working relationship between the superior and subordinate. A healthy relationship between supervisors and subordinates significantly impacts the overall culture of the organization and employees' emotional attachment to work (Azeem et al., 2024). Research has shown that individuals working in financial institutions such as banks, particularly in developing countries like Pakistan, are often subjected to emotional and psychological stress due to factors such as overcrowding, workload, and lack of autonomy (Idrees et al., 2017; Manzoor & Jahangir, 2024). The fundamental significance of the idea of alienation has also been linked to a person's dissociative state (a cognitive experience of separation) in connection to another aspect of their environment (Aksakalli, 2024). However, despite its significance in the organizations, studies on alienation among white-collar workers are scarce in Pakistan.

According to research attribution disagreement between a leader and a subordinate is related to the intentions and satisfaction of the subordinate to leave the organization. In a similar vein, having bad relationships with your superiors could contribute to feeling alienated. Thus, phubbing from the boss, being negative feedback, seems associated with perceived work alienation of the subordinates, which needs empirical evidences (Hasan et al., 2024). Only 13 % of workers in Pakistani industry actually feel engaged in their assigned organizational task, while other 87% do not have any attachment with their work. (Rafiq et al., 2023).

Employee self- efficacy has a mediating role while checking the outcomes of phubbing behavior. Therefore, the mediating effect of employee self-efficacy between the relationship of boss phubbing and employees' perceived work alienation is proposed. Phubbing can happen anywhere; however, phubbing's impact could be more substantial when it occurs between close relations or situations where there is a high level of interaction between the parties, such as the relationship between a boss and their subordinates (Khan et al., 2021).

1.2 Research Questions

- 1 Does boss phubbing impact the employees' perceived work alienation?
- 2 Does boss phubbing impact the employee self-efficacy?
- 3 Does employee self-efficacy impact the employees' perceived work alienation?
- 4 Does employee self-efficacy mediate between boss phubbing and employees' perceived work alienation?

1.3 Research Objectives

- 1 To evaluate the impact of boss phubbing on employees' perceived work alienation.
- 2 To check the influence of boss phubbing on employee self-efficacy.
- 3 To check the impact of employee self-efficacy on their work alienation.
- 4 To check the mediating role of employee self-efficacy between boss phubbing and employees' perceived work alienation.

Although such emotive workplace events, like phubbing and its responses were previously neglected, they should not have been neglected theoretically nor empirically.

The findings also suggest that, as research on phubbing is still at its early development stage, the impact of phubbing behavior in diverse situations warrants close scrutiny in future researches. This gap in the literature is filled by examining whether employee self-efficacy plays a mediating role in the relationship between boss phubbing and worker-reported job alienation. Self-efficacy, which involves the extent to which a person believes he or she can perform a job competently and bring about desired outcomes, is known to be highly influential in determining how individuals will respond to situations of stress or challenge. Therefore, understanding whether self-efficacy mediates the relationship between boss phubbing and employees' perceived job alienation is very important. This can enable firms to craft solutions that directly target boss phubbing and its negative consequences on employees' outcomes by revealing the underlying routes through which boss phubbing influences their work experience.

2. Literature Review

Perceived work alienation of employees is a psychological condition that reflects the extent to which employees experience a sense of distance from their own job and the organization they work for (Yasami et al., 2024). It is the sense of disconnect or aloneness from your work, colleagues, and self. Boss phubbing occurs when a boss uses their phone or other digital devices during meetings or conversations with employees, sending messages of disrespect, inattention, and a lack of concern for those who report to them. This may be viewed as workplace incivility, which is linked to employee well-being, work satisfaction and organizational commitment (Emmanuel & Das, 2024).

It is also hypothesized that workplace incivility, particularly by higher-level management, is associated with increased feelings of helplessness and detachment among employees, thereby enhancing work alienation. When there is a sense of not being valued and taken seriously by one's boss, it can also lead to a sense of disengagement and detachment from work and the organization (De Clercq et al., 2019; Niven et al., 2021). The established research on workplace communication, technology use and employee well-being might help to better understand how boss phubbing affects Employees' perceived work alienation (Srivastava et al., 2024). Individuals can suffer from work alienation, a state of mind popularized by Marx in which they are alienated from the work itself because they do not feel like it helps them fulfill their most basic needs and desires.

Meanwhile, employee self-efficacy represents an individual's confidence that he or she can execute a course of action to achieve desired outcomes in the workplace (Aman-Ullah et al., 2024). It is one of the key factors for employee motivation, performance and well-being at work. Indeed, it is believed that individuals with firm self-efficacy beliefs are more likely to achieve difficult goals, stick to them despite failure, and succeed in their endeavors (Mohamad & Abiddin, 2024).

Employee self-efficacy is the conviction that one can carry out a particular task or job satisfactorily. It is an essential part of worker performance, motivation, and well-being at work. Self-efficacy theory was first proposed by Bandura (1969, 1977) who proposed that people's conduct and results are influenced by their self-perceptions. In Bandura's view, individuals with high self-efficacy are more likely to set difficult objectives, persevere through difficulties, and succeed in their endeavors (Gagné et al., 2022).

Research revealed that rude supervisor behavior, such as boss phubbing, negatively affected workers' feelings of self-efficacy, job satisfaction, and emotional

weariness (Yasin et al., 2020). Similarly, another study found that workers who witnessed rude behavior from their managers had lower self-efficacy, which in turn affected their intentions to leave and job satisfaction (Ali et al., 2016).

Employee self-efficacy is strongly correlated with workplace communication because it affects how employees view their own abilities and themselves (Panatik et al., 2011). Workers who witnessed rude behavior from their managers had lower self-efficacy, which in turn affected their intentions to leave and job satisfaction (Kakkar et al., 2022). Organizational research has examined the relationship between workers' perceptions of work alienation and their self-efficacy. Finally, a study examined the relationship between self-efficacy and work alienation among Chinese migrant workers (Cho et al., 2016). Furthermore, the study revealed that self-efficacy is negatively related to work alienation, suggesting that workers with high self-efficacy may experience less work alienation. The Self-Efficacy theory states that an individual's motivation, behavior, and outcomes are caused by the belief that they can accomplish a task or reach a goal (Singh & Randhawa, 2024).

Weiss and Cropanzano (1996) provided a more rational explanation of this situation in the form of Affective Events Theory (AET). The relevance of phubbing as an effective event in the context of AET is the central focus of this study. Weiss and Cropanzano (1996) explained that employees experience a range of pleasant and negative feelings in response to everyday business events, or "affective events." Basch and Fisher (2000) narrated that job-related stimuli, object, or event is defined as "an incident that stimulates (appraisal of and emotional reaction to a temporary or ongoing job-related agent, object, or event" (Sankar, 2025; Yousaf et al., 2022). According to Weiss and Cropanzano (1996), the happenings and outcomes of employees' interactions with the organizational environment elicit emotional attitudes and behavioral responses at work (Iqbal et al., 2025; Zalesny et al., 1985). At the workplace, the prevailing atmosphere affects employees' emotions, thoughts, moods, attitudes, and behaviors. People's attitudes and behaviors can shape an organization's culture and tone. Organizational researchers are interested in this subject since both components influence one another. Organizations have a specific environment made up of various job requirements, job qualities, and job resources that affect employees' emotions because of specific positive or bad behaviors (Wright, 2004).

Affective Events Theory (AET) further emphasizes that not all workplace events carry the same emotional weight; instead, their impact depends on the frequency, intensity, and relational context in which they occur. Boss phubbing, a relatively silent behavior and gradually even accepted as a routine in current jobs is categorized as one of the micro-incivility event that becomes more salient when accumulated over time (Yasin et al., 2020). In supervisory roles in which subordinates rely on guidance, empathy, and validation from their supervisor, short phone-checking incidents may be perceived as social rejection. AET proposes that this cumulative exposure to negative cues constructs an emotional script through which employees evaluate their job, value, and relationship with their supervisor. As things pile up, employee's affective states of mind move toward frustration, demotivation and emotional detachment – all pathways to work alienation. Boss phubbing is a newly emerged form of emotionally harmful leader behavior, and it can be well explained by AET (Schmidt-Barad & Chernyak-Hai, 2024).

The issue of phubbing has been extensively studied, primarily in the neurological (Zhan

et al., 2022) and sociological domains (Al-Saggaf & Macculloch, 2019) with a focus on its impact on romantic relationships (David & Roberts, 2021; Zhan et al., 2022). Additionally, (Khan et al., 2021) state that studies have been conducted in developed and Western countries, leaving developing countries like Pakistan largely unexplored (Ansari et al., 2024). Despite the fact that financial institutions such as banks are the backbone of the economy, no research has been conducted to date (Khan et al., 2021). Similarly, previous research in this domain is lacking a theoretical foundation (Khan et al., 2021). Thus, further research is needed to fill this gap by grounding it in theoretical foundations and to provide insights into the potential negative consequences of boss phubbing in the workplace.

The current study will be a valuable addition to relevant literature as well as for organizational executives and academics, enabling them to formulate strategies to be aware of their Supervisory positions can be improved by better understanding phubbing as a boss's impolite behavior and its previously identified negative effects (Yasin et al., 2020). Additionally, this study will help managers appreciate the implications of phubbing, an often-emotional phenomenon, by clarifying its nature and effects.

2.1 Schematic Diagram

2.2 Hypotheses

H1. Boss phubbing has a significant positive impact on employees’ perceived work alienation.

H2. Boss phubbing has a significantly negative impact on employee self-efficacy.

H3. Employee self-efficacy has a significantly negative impact on employees’ work alienation.

H4. Employee self-efficacy significantly mediates the relationship between boss phubbing and employees’ perceived work alienation.

3. Research Methodology

The current study is explanatory and quantitative. The components of a research design primarily included a positive research philosophy and a survey strategy with deductive approach. The sampling strategy was employed and cross-sectional method was used to collect information.

Statistical Package for variance-based structural equation modeling by using Smart PLS, was used for data analysis (Jahangir, Saraih, et al., 2025; Peng & Chan, 2019; Youssef & Luthans, 2007). Blunch, 2013 recommended that one should use variance-based structural equation modeling when “the analysis is concerned with testing a theoretical framework from a prediction perspective”. Data reliability and validity was

evaluated by computing Cronbach’s alpha (CA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The SEM measurement model considered data validity and reliability in interpretation (Afthanorhan et al., 2020; Guay et al., 2014; Hafeez et al., 2023).

One of the significant benefits of PLS modeling over other analytical methods was that it simultaneously handled multiple predictors and multiple response variables (Zhao et al., 2020). In contrast, regression analysis can handle only one regressor at a time (Blunch, 2013). So, this was a well-suited method, as is widely used in several research projects to estimate route coefficients in structural models (Afthanorhan et al., 2020).

3.1 Measurement Development

The research instruments used for this study were adapted from the literature to collect data from the respondents. A summary of the scales used in this study is given below.

Table 1: Research Instrument Construct and Source

Variable	No of Items	Developed by	Anchor
Boss Phubbing	9 items	Roberts and David, (2017)	5 Point Likert
Self-Efficacy	3 items	Spreitzer, (1995)	5 Point Likert
Employees’ Perceived Work Alienation	10 items	Hirschfeld et al., (2000).	5 Point Likert

3.2 Data Collection

Data for this study were collected through a structured questionnaire administered to frontline employees working in the banking sector of the Rawalpindi–Islamabad region. A total of 550 questionnaires were distributed, out of which 510 were returned, reflecting a strong initial response. After carefully screening the returned forms for completeness, consistency, and missing values, 24 responses were excluded for incomplete or improperly filled-out information. The final dataset comprised 486 valid and usable responses, which served as the basis for all subsequent analyses. This robust sample size ensured adequate statistical power for the measurement and structural model assessments conducted in the study.

3.3 Results

3.3.1 Demographic Analysis

The demographic profile of the 486 respondents in Table 2 shows that the majority were male (88.5%), while only 11.5% were female, reflecting the male-dominated nature of frontline banking roles in the region. Most respondents were between 26 and 30 years old (35.8%), followed by those aged 31–35 years (28%), indicating a predominantly young and mid-career workforce. In terms of education, Bachelor’s degree holders constituted the largest group (49%), followed by Master’s degree holders (39.1%), showing that the banking sector attracts well-qualified individuals. Job specification data revealed that 61.7% of participants worked as frontline staff, with smaller proportions in back-office (23%) and supervisory roles (15.2%). Regarding work experience, most respondents had between 1–3 years (34.2%) or 4–6 years (31.3%) of experience, reflecting a relatively stable employee base with moderate tenure.

Table 2: Demographic Analysis

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	430	88.50%
	Female	56	11.50%
Age	20–25 years	98	20.20%
	26–30 years	174	35.80%
	31–35 years	136	28.00%
	Above 35 years	78	16.00%
Education	Bachelor’s Degree	238	49.00%
	Master’s Degree	190	39.10%
	MS/MPhil	46	9.50%
	Other	12	2.50%
Job Specification	Frontline Staff	300	61.70%
	Back-office Staff	112	23.00%
	Supervisory Level	74	15.20%
Experience	Less than 1 year	60	12.30%
	1–3 years	166	34.20%
	4–6 years	152	31.30%
	More than 6 years	108	22.20%

3.3.2 Data Reliability and Validity

The measurement model in Table 3 demonstrates strong item reliability, as all factor loadings for the constructs—Boss Phubbing, Employee Self-Efficacy, and Employees’ Perceived Work Alienation—are above the recommended threshold of 0.70. This indicates that each item sufficiently represents its respective construct. Cronbach’s Alpha values of 0.897 for Boss Phubbing, 0.909 for Employee Self-Efficacy, and 0.720 for Perceived Work Alienation further confirm internal consistency and reliability. Similarly, the composite reliability values (ρ_a and ρ_c) for all constructs exceed the accepted minimum criteria, demonstrating that the measurement scales consistently capture the intended latent variables.

Table 3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Data Reliability and Validity

Constructs/Items	FL	CA	CR (rho_a)	CR (rho_c)	AVE
Boss Phubbing		0.897	0.897	0.916	0.548
BPG1	0.738				
BPG2	0.732				
BPG3	0.725				
BPG4	0.738				
BPG5	0.753				
BPG6	0.740				
BPG7	0.753				
BPG8	0.748				
BPG9	0.736				
Employee Self-Efficacy		0.909	0.910	0.924	0.549
EPA1	0.747				
EPA10	0.736				
EPA2	0.744				
EPA3	0.730				
EPA4	0.759				
EPA5	0.738				
EPA6	0.760				
EPA7	0.727				
EPA8	0.720				
EPA9	0.749				
Employee's Perceived Work Alienation		0.720	0.720	0.843	0.641
SEF1	0.823				
SEF2	0.795				
SEF3	0.783				

Convergent validity is also established, as the AVE values for Boss Phubbing (0.548), Employee Self-Efficacy (0.549), and Employees' Perceived Work Alienation (0.641) surpass the minimum benchmark of 0.50. This confirms that each construct explains more than half of the variance in its indicators. Collectively, these results affirm that the measurement model is robust, reliable, and valid, providing a strong foundation for proceeding to the structural model analysis and hypothesis testing. Figure 2 also shows the CFA and R-square values.

Figure 2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis and R-Square Values

The discriminant validity results in Table 3, assessed using the HTMT criterion, indicate that the constructs in the model are sufficiently distinct from one another. The HTMT value between Boss Phubbing and Employee’s Perceived Work Alienation is 0.813, while the value between Boss Phubbing and Employee Self-Efficacy is 0.833; both remain below the maximum acceptable threshold of 0.85, demonstrating adequate discriminant validity. Similarly, the HTMT value between Employee Self-Efficacy and Employees’ Perceived Work Alienation is 0.862, which falls below the more lenient upper limit of 0.90, further supporting the distinction between these constructs. Overall, these results confirm that Boss Phubbing, Employee Self-Efficacy, and Employees’ Perceived Work Alienation measure distinct theoretical concepts with minimal overlap, thereby strengthening the structural model.

Table 4: Discriminant Validity

	BPG	EPA	SEF
BPG			
EPA	0.813		
SEF	0.833	0.862	

The results in Table 4 show that the model explains a substantial amount of variance in Employees’ Perceived Alienation (EPA), with an R-square value of 0.620. This indicates that boss-phubbing and self-efficacy together account for approximately 62% of the variation in EPA, which is considered a strong explanatory power in behavioral and organizational research. The adjusted R-square (0.618) remains almost identical, suggesting that the model is stable and not over-fitted, and that the predictors included are theoretically and statistically meaningful.

For Self-Efficacy (SEF), the R-square is 0.449, which indicates that boss-phubbing explains about 45% of the variance in employees’ self-efficacy. This represents a moderate-to-substantial level of predictive power and highlights that boss-phubbing is an important determinant of employees’ perceived competence at work. The similar adjusted value (0.448) further confirms the explanatory strength of this model. Overall,

the R² results demonstrate that the proposed model possesses a good level of predictive relevance for key endogenous constructs.

Table 5: R-Square Values

	R-square	R-square adjusted
EPA	0.620	0.618
SEF	0.449	0.448

The model fit indicators suggest that the proposed structural model demonstrates a satisfactory level of goodness-of-fit. The SRMR value of 0.043 is well below the commonly accepted threshold of 0.08, indicating acceptable model fit and a low average discrepancy between observed and predicted correlations. The d_{ULS} (0.478) and d_G (0.141) values also fall within acceptable limits, showing that the discrepancy between empirical and model-implied matrices is minimal. Moreover, the reported Chi-square value (380.066), although typically sensitive to sample size, supports the adequacy of the model when interpreted alongside other fit indices. Finally, the NFI value of 0.928 exceeds the recommended cut-off of 0.90, further confirming that the model exhibits a good comparative fit and adequately represents the observed data.

Table 6: Model Fit Values

	Saturated model
SRMR	0.043
d_{ULS}	0.478
d_G	0.141
Chi-square	380.066
NFI	0.928

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values reported for all measurement items are well below the common threshold of 5, indicating that multicollinearity is not a concern in this study. The VIF values for the Boss-Phubbing (BPG) items range from approximately 1.72 to 1.87, while the Employees' Perceived Alienation (EPA) items lie between 1.77 and 1.95, which demonstrates acceptable levels of collinearity. Similarly, the Self-Efficacy (SEF) items show even lower VIF values (between 1.37 and 1.49), further confirming the absence of problematic multicollinearity. These results support the reliability of the measurement items and indicate that each item contributes unique information to its corresponding construct without redundancy or inflation of explanatory power.

Table 7: Multicollinearity

Items	VIF
BPG1	1.771
BPG2	1.774
BPG3	1.721
BPG4	1.773
BPG5	1.835
BPG6	1.775
BPG7	1.868
BPG8	1.818
BPG9	1.771
EPA1	1.867

EPA10	1.788
EPA2	1.891
EPA3	1.781
EPA4	1.952
EPA5	1.847
EPA6	1.921
EPA7	1.774
EPA8	1.772
EPA9	1.896
SEF1	1.495
SEF2	1.392
SEF3	1.375

3.3.3 Path Analysis

Based on the reported structural-path coefficients, the table 7 shows that Boss-Phubbing (BPG) has a significant and meaningful direct effect on Employees' Perceived Alienation (EPA) ($\beta = 0.488$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher supervisor phone-use during interactions is associated with a higher level of alienation felt by employees. At the same time, BPG significantly reduces employees' self-efficacy (SEF) ($\beta = -0.670$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that frequent boss-phubbing deteriorates employees' feelings of competence and capability at work. All t-statistics are far above the critical value of 1.96, confirming the significance of these direct links.

Table 8: Path Analysis

Hypotheses	β	SD	T statistics	P values	Results
BPG -> EPA	0.488	0.047	10.296	0	Positively Accepted
BPG -> SEF	-0.67	0.027	25.112	0	Negatively Accepted
SEF -> EPA	-0.372	0.048	7.82	0	Negatively Accepted
BPG -> SEF -> EPA	0.249	0.034	7.417	0	Positively Accepted

Furthermore, the negative association between self-efficacy (SEF) and perceived alienation (EPA) ($\beta = -0.372$, $p < 0.001$) implies that employees who feel less self-efficacious tend to report stronger alienation—consistent with psychological and organizational behavior theory. Finally, the indirect path (BPG \rightarrow SEF \rightarrow EPA) is also statistically significant ($\beta = 0.249$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that boss-phubbing increases alienation not only directly but also indirectly through dropping employees' self-efficacy. In other words, self-efficacy moderately mediates the relationship and thus acts as an important psychological process explaining how boss-phubbing advances employee alienation. Path analysis values are also shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Path Analysis

3.4 Discussion

The findings indicate the positive correlation between boss-phubbing and employees perceived work alienation, which means that when employees perceive there is more supervisor phone-use, then they are more likely to feel excluded socially and psychologically. Such a relationship is theoretically consistent with Affective Events Theory, which states that negative supervisory behaviors are emotional stressors that influence the way employees experience and evaluate work events.

Boss-phubbing has a negative and significant effect on employee self-efficacy, which means that when superiors are digitally distracted, it implies lower levels of performance and confidence in the tasks by employees. This adverse effect can be explained in terms of inadequate managerial attention, fewer developmental cues and lower quality feedback at work which are necessary for the overall cultivation of employees' perceived self-efficacy. From the social-cognitive perspective, employees learn through verbal persuasion, observation and supervisory support, thus a distracted boss signals the absence of these developmental mechanisms and consequently weakens self-efficacy (Chiles & Zorn, 1995). Previous studies have likewise reported that employees' psychological resources decline when supervisors engage in inattentive digital communication practices (Braun et al., 2015).

The findings confirmed a significant negative association between self-efficacy and employees' perceived work alienation, indicating that employees who feel less competent are more likely to perceive their work environment as isolating and psychologically distant. This is consistent with the argument that employees with lower psychological resources experience higher emotional fatigue, disengagement and detachment, all of which are classic characteristics of work alienation. The results also reinforce the notion that self-efficacy functions as a personal resource that protects employees from alienating work experiences by increasing autonomy, perceived control and work meaningfulness. This finding is in line with previous research that reported similar negative associations between self-efficacy and alienation-related outcomes (Rubin et al., 1993; Vancouver et al., 2014).

Finally, a mediation analysis showed that the homophobic phubbing had a significant mediating effect on work alienation through self-efficacy, which means that low self-efficacy may partially explain why leading by digital distraction can cause people to feel alienated. Such chain mediation implies that boss-phubbing constructs employees' internalization psychological appraisal in the process of working on their

competence and work quality in addition to the relational consequences at an immediate level.

4. Conclusion

The current study sought to investigate the correlation between employee-perceived boss-phubbing and workplace alienation, as well as the mediating effect of individual sense of efficacy on this relationship. The results indicated that supervisory smartphone use during face-to-face engagement is a driver of employees' reported experiences of ostracism, suggesting that digital interruptions serve as an understated yet profound source of inattentiveness in the workplace. It was also established in this research that boss-phubbing has an important negative effect on employee self-efficacy, implying that supervisory neglect leads to employees' professional inefficiency. Furthermore, findings are consistent with self-efficacy as a partial mediator of this relationship, such that digital managerial behavior not only has a direct influence on individual workplace responses but also reduces employees' sense of competence. This study provides theoretical and practical contributions that extend our understanding of boss phubbing and foster a nascent managerial issue that should receive strategic organizational attention. The results highlight the basic fact that we need to look at leadership in the digital age, not only as efficient and information-laden, but also from an interpersonal point of view, looking into what it means for us as leaders on a psychological level.

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